

APPLICATION OF GRADIENT BASED IMAGE SEGMENTATION TO SAR IMAGERY

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ABSTRACT

In the current paper, we explore the use of a gradient based region growing method to segment Synthetic Aperture radar (SAR) imagery into disjoint regions and later categorize them into one of several known classes. Segment based features, as opposed to pixel based features, are utilized in the supervised classification stage. The method is tested on SAR images acquired from RADARSAT-2 and AIRSAR sensors. Here, SAR amplitude data and/or features from Pauli, Cloude-Pottier decompositions are used for segmentation and classification. Qualitative and quantitative results show good identification of open-water, terrain and agricultural areas.

Index Terms— Synthetic aperture radar, Image segmentation, Image classification

1. INTRODUCTION

Synthetic aperture radar (SAR) is a remote sensing modality which provides complex-valued measurements for scene reflectivity of microwave radiation. The use of microwave radiation provides the capacity for all weather, day/night imaging. The deployment of commercial (i.e. RadarSat-2, COSMO-SkyMed, TerraSAR) and civil (Sentinel-1) spaceborne SAR systems over the past decade have changed the world of SAR from a traditionally data poor, to an increasingly data rich environment [1]. These systems provide variable capabilities including polarization (i.e. single-, dual-, and/or quad-pol), radiation wavelength (i.e. C- or X-band), and resolution (1 - 20 m). In order to take full advantage of the increase in the amount and diversity of available SAR imagery, it is vital to develop a diverse set of techniques for automated processing of SAR imagery into information content. It is important to note here that due to the granularity or speckle in SAR imagery [2], many automated segmentation/classification techniques used for traditional electro-optical imagery demonstrate poor performance when applied to SAR imagery. Segmentation methods have been developed for and applied to single-, dual- and quad-pol SAR imagery. These methods vary in complexity from simplistic histogram thresholding of single-

pol amplitude imagery to region-based classification of complex-valued quad-pol SAR images using Markov random fields [3].

One area of application for SAR image segmentation and classification is the automated detection of open-water during flooding events. This is partly due to its ability to penetrate cloud cover. The specular scattering of microwaves by open-water results in areas of low return in SAR imagery. The most prevalent method used for the segmentation of open-water in SAR imagery is histogram thresholding. Martinis et al. [4] extended this to utilize an object based image analysis approach by applying histogram based thresholding to regions segmented by a multi-resolution segmentation technique.

In this paper, the SAR image is initially segmented into disjoint regions by a gradient driven region growing method and then the regions are categorized into multiple classes by a supervised classification method. This is a direct extension of the segmentation algorithm that has been applied to color [5], multi/hyperspectral [6], bio-medical and video imagery. In previous work [6], the segmentation algorithm was able to delineate water regions in multi/hyperspectral imagery due to the use of textural information and region growing.

2. PROPOSED METHOD

Antennas of SAR systems transmit and receive polarized EM waves. Most often orthogonal horizontal (H) and vertical (V) polarized waves are utilized for transmission and reception. Based on the transmitter-receiver operation, complex single (e.g. S_{HH}), dual (e.g. S_{HH} and S_{HV} - transmit H & receive V) or quad (S_{HH} , S_{HV} , S_{VH} and S_{VV}) scattering coefficients produced by target can be measured. In the fully polarimetric system, the scatter matrix (S) [1] measured by radar is given by equation 1.

$$[S] = \begin{bmatrix} S_{HH} & S_{VH} \\ S_{HV} & S_{VV} \end{bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

The data can be projected onto multiple basis. In Pauli decomposition, the data is projected onto a basis which represents single bounce, double bounce and volume scattering. A pseudocolor image with $R=|S_{HH}-S_{VV}|$, $G=|2S_{HV}|$, $B=|S_{HH}-S_{VV}|$ is used for visualization (Pauli

image). To describe distributed scatters, second-order coherency or covariance matrix and subsequent decomposition are needed. One such decomposition, Cloude-Pottier method, generates entropy (H), alpha (α) and anisotropy (A) parameters.

The proposed segmentation algorithm consists of 1) preprocessing 2) gradient computation, and 3) region growing, followed by a 4) classification step. The method begins with speckle filtering of the input SAR data. Speckle noise occurs in SAR images due to coherent summation of reflectance from multiple objects present within a resolution cell. A Boxcar or Lee filter is applied to reduce the speckle noise.

2.1. Gradient based segmentation

In the second step, the gradient of the SAR image (I) is computed either by a scalar (single band) or vector (multi-band) gradient approach. In both the methods, individual bands are first blurred by a Gaussian kernel (size 7×7 and sigma 1) to reduce variance and generate a smooth gradient image. Forward difference of the smoothed image is found in x and y spatial directions. For the scalar case, gradient at each pixel location is given by equation 2.

$$G = \sqrt{(\partial I / \partial x)^2 + (\partial I / \partial y)^2} \quad (2)$$

$$J_w = \begin{bmatrix} w_1(\partial I_1 / \partial x) & w_1(\partial I_1 / \partial y) \\ \vdots & \vdots \\ w_b(\partial I_b / \partial x) & w_b(\partial I_b / \partial y) \end{bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

In vector gradient approach, at each pixel location, a Jacobian matrix is constructed using the forward differences computed. Individual SAR bands (I_1, \dots, I_b) could have varying level of gradient information and hence the Jacobian matrix is scaled by weighting factors (w_1, \dots, w_b) [7].

Following this, the inner product ($J_w^T J_w$) of the matrix and its corresponding largest eigenvalue is found. The square root of the largest eigenvalue represents the gradient magnitude [8] at a given pixel location. It should be noted that the Gaussian smoothing is done only for computing the gradient image (G) and the original speckle filtered SAR image is used in the subsequent region growing (spectral similarity) and classification steps.

In the region growing [6] stage, initial seeds are selected from homogeneous regions of the image and iteratively merged with similar adjacent seeds of increasing gradient value. This growth process concludes at edge locations thus generating an over segmented result. Region growing is implemented by utilizing the gradient image. Connected pixel groups whose: (1) gradient magnitude value is less than a threshold (G_1), and (2) size is greater than a set value (S_m) are chosen as the initial seeds (parent seeds). Following this, the threshold G_1 is incremented by a step size (ΔG). New pixel groups whose gradient magnitude falls between

G_1 and $G_1 + \Delta G$, form child seeds. Spectral dissimilarity between the parent seeds and its neighboring child seeds are found. If the value is less than a threshold (T_{sp}), the child seeds are merged with parent seeds. The merging process is iterated by introducing seeds of increasing gradient. At regular intervals, additional seeds consisting of pixels that are dissimilar or non-adjacent to parent seeds are included in the growth process. This step avoids under-segmentation of the image. Intervals for seed addition are chosen adaptively based on the histogram of the gradient image. The histogram is split into N (20) intervals each spanning equal image area.

2.2. Object-based Supervised Classification

In the final step of the algorithm, each SAR image segment are assigned a target category using support vector machine (SVM). It is a supervised classification approach that involves training and testing. During training, a model is generally learnt from a dataset which consist of image features and known class labels. The SVM [9] method, in particular, finds a hyperplane in the feature space that optimally separates two classes. When a test sample is introduced, it is classified as either of the classes based on the side of the plane the test feature falls into. For a multi-class problem, one-against-one or one-against-all combinations are evaluated to assign a label to the test sample. Kernel functions allow implicit mapping of the input feature space onto a higher dimensional space. Features are implicitly mapped to higher dimensional space (by kernel functions) for better class separation. SVM is a robust method for classification and is resistant to over fitting.

For our approach, the SVM classifier is trained on pixel features in the training set. Multiple features of SAR imagery, such as (a) the amplitude images, (b) Pauli vectors and (c) H, alpha, and anisotropy polarimetric parameters, are used. Features of each SAR image segment (obtained at the conclusion of region growing) are averaged and assigned to the entire region. This segment-averaged image is classified by the SVM. Object based classification accuracy will be high if the segmentation boundaries agree with real object contours in the image.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The segmentation algorithm is demonstrated on two SAR images: RadarSat-2 Fine Quad-Pol image of San Francisco (SF), USA (figure 1; azimuth resolution 5.2 m; range resolution 8.0 m; footprint size 130 km²; incidence angle 2) [10], and AIRSAR L-band image of Flevoland, NL [11] (figure 2; Pauli RGB image). The stretched appearance of the SAR imagery in comparison with the google maps (figure 1) satellite representation is due to data being in the slant plane and the asymmetry in the azimuth and range resolutions. Note that satellite and SAR imagery shown were acquired at different times. Matlab programming language

was primarily utilized for SAR data extraction, filtering, and segmentation. In addition, LIBSVM [12] software package was used for SVM-based classification and PolSARPro software [11] was employed for AIRSAR L-band Flevoland data extraction and H, alpha and A data generation. Running the segmentation-classification procedure on the high resolution SAR image would require substantial computational memory. Consequently, the image was split into 512x512 sub-images and these blocks were individually segmented and classified. For segmentation, the spectral threshold (T_{sp}) is empirically set at 1000 for 16-bit images and 30 for 8-bit images (AIRSAR Pauli image). Best kernel for SVM and its optimal parameter were found through exhaustive search (cross-validation on training data). Radial basis function kernel gave best validation results for both the SAR images (gamma and cost values were different for each setting).

We analyzed the segmentation-classification outcome of the SF image under two different settings: 1) $|S_{HH}|$ data for segmentation and $|S_{HH}|$, $|S_{HV}|$ for classification; 2) Pauli image ($|S_{HH}+S_{VV}|$, $|S_{HH}-S_{VV}|$, $|2S_{HV}|$) for segmentation and $|S_{HH}+S_{VV}|$, $|S_{HH}-S_{VV}|$, $|2S_{HV}|$, H, alpha and A for classification. Samples were chosen from five classes similar to Uhlmann et.al. [13]. These classes, namely, water (blue), urban (red), urban developed (pink), developed (yellow) and vegetation (green) were utilized to train the SVM classifier. The result of segmentation-classification for the $|S_{HH}|$, $|S_{HV}|$ setting is shown in figure 1b. Most of the open-water areas were identified properly when compared with expectation derived from the google map satellite image (subfigure 1f). Parts of Oakland region is misclassified as water in the $|S_{HH}|$, $|S_{HV}|$ setting. This is due the fact, the particular area has low return signal in both the S_{HH} , S_{HV} configuration. Figure 1c shows the results for the Pauli image setting. Since additional features were utilized for classification, urban and developed areas are classified better in comparison to $|S_{HH}|$ and $|S_{HV}|$ result.

To quantitatively evaluate the gradient based approach, we utilize the AIRSAR L-band image of Flevoland, ND and the corresponding ground truth data made available by Yu et al [14]. The Pauli color coded image and its ground truth consisting of eight classes: Peas, Beet, Bare Soil, Rapeseed, Lucerne, Potatoes, Barley and wheat are shown in figure 2a and 2b respectively. Twenty percent of pixels from each class was selected to determine the optimal gamma, cost values and generate the SVM model. Pauli image was segmented into regions and the features: $|S_{HH}+S_{VV}|$, $|S_{HH}-S_{VV}|$, $|2S_{HV}|$, H, alpha and A, extracted from those regions were used for classification. Figures 2c and 2d, show the segmentation and classification results respectively. The classification result overlaid over the ground truth mask is shown in figure 2e. The main source of mis-classification, as visualized through figure 2e, is at the boundaries where neighboring regions overshoot their edges. Table 1 shows the confusion matrix for all the classes. Our method achieves

an overall mean accuracy of 97.3%. We compare our results with two other region based approaches: the region based Wisher MRF method [3] and unsupervised PolGRIS method [14]. They attain an accuracy of 95.4% and 98.2% respectively. Note that our method uses training data for classification, whereas the PolGRIS is an unsupervised method. The proposed method has a higher accuracy (98.98) for the class Beet in comparison to the Yu et al [14] method (87.6%). But the overall accuracy is slightly lower due to misclassification at the boundaries.

	Peas	Beet	Bare Soil	Rapeseed	Lucrene	Wheat	Potatoes	Barley
Peas	89.20	0.86	0.00	0.33	0.00	4.95	0.00	4.67
Beet	0.48	98.98	0.00	0.13	0.00	0.13	0.04	0.25
Bare Soil	0.00	0.03	97.86	1.85	0.00	0.25	0.00	0.00
Rapeseed	0.01	0.01	0.00	98.93	0.00	1.05	0.00	0.00
Lucrene	2.43	0.56	0.00	0.12	96.27	0.62	0.00	0.00
Wheat	0.00	0.86	0.00	0.00	0.00	98.84	0.00	0.30
Potatoes	0.60	0.11	0.00	0.14	0.00	0.09	99.07	0.00
Barley	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.30	0.00	99.70

Table 1: Confusion matrix for the classification results of AIRSAR Flevoland image

This work successfully demonstrates the application of a gradient based segmentation algorithm to single and multi-band SAR imagery. Our future work will involve fusion of additional information, e.g. Texture, DEM, optical imagery data, with SAR images for accurate identification of open-water areas, and perform quantitative evaluation. In addition, we will improve the region growing module to identify narrow, inland water areas.

4. REFERENCES

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Figure 1. RadarSat-2 image [10] of San Francisco. (a) Pauli color coded (RGB) image of complex SAR image in the slant plane. (b) Segment-based classification result achieved by using $|S_{HH}|$ data for segmentation and $|S_{HH}|$, $|S_{HV}|$ for classification. (c) Result achieved by using Pauli image for segmentation and $|S_{HH}+S_{VV}|$, $|S_{HH}-S_{VV}|$, $|2S_{HV}|$, H , α and A for classification. (d) pixel-based classification ($|S_{HH}+S_{VV}|$, $|S_{HH}-S_{VV}|$, $|2S_{HV}|$, H , α and A). (e) Google maps satellite image of the approximate scene in the SAR image.

Figure 2. AIRSAR image [11] of Flevoland, ND. (a) Pauli color coded image of complex SAR image. (b) Classes. (c) Ground truth map. (d) Segmentation result. (e) Classification result ($|S_{HH}+S_{VV}|$, $|S_{HH}-S_{VV}|$, $|2S_{HV}|$, H , A , α features). (f) Classification result overlaid on the ground truth mask.